

Antimicrobial and Antibiofilm Activity of L-Arginase Produced by *Streptomyces* sp. HAB 228

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ABSTRACT

Several antibiotics are presently available in the market that are reported to be active against opportunistic pathogens such as *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus mutans*. On entering host immune system these infectious bacteria are difficult to treat due to pre-existing drug resistance mechanisms and also through their biofilm forming abilities. Thus, demanding alternative therapeutic strategies for targeting drug resistant and biofilm forming bacteria. The purified L-arginase inhibited the growth of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus mutans* under *in-vitro* conditions. Antimicrobial and antibiofilm forming ability of L-arginase enzyme produced by *Streptomyces* sp. HAB 228 is noted. It is also observed that the reduction in biofilm formation being 57±4%, 54±6% and 29±4% of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Streptococcus mutans* and *Staphylococcus aureus* respectively by 25 U of L-arginase.

KEY WORDS: antimicrobial, antibiofilm, biofilm, L-arginase, *Streptomyces* sp.

INTRODUCTION:

Pseudomonas aeruginosa, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus mutans* are generally linked with both acute and chronic infections of humans and animals like dental diseases, ear infections, eye infections, urinary tract infections, implant rejections etc.^[1] They generally resist antibiotic treatment due to various reasons predominantly including their ability to form biofilms.

Biofilm is a complex biological system comprising of extracellular matrix (exopolysaccharide) of microorganisms along with proteins, lipids, nucleic acids dynamic and is comparatively less defined micro-habitat^[2]. Biofilms formed by the pathogenic microorganisms are detrimental not only for human health but also for industries since they cause blockade and corrosion of filters, pipelines, storage tanks etc^[3].

L-arginase, an enzyme that hydrolyses L-arginine into ornithine and urea is gaining importance

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now-a-days due to its anticancer effects.^[4] Various microorganisms like *Cyanobacteria*, *Bacillus anthracis*, *Arthrobacter* sp. KUJ 8602, *Agaricusbisporus* etc, have been reported to produce L-arginase. L-arginine is considered as one of the most important precursor and intermediate in metabolic cycle^[5,6,7]. Hence, limiting its supply by L-arginase supplementation may lead to inhibition in growth of microorganisms and/ or formation of biofilm by microorganisms. Thus the present study was conducted to assess antimicrobial and antibiofilm effects of L-arginase produced by *Streptomyces* sp.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

L-arginase production and purification: The production of L-arginase was done on Czapek Dox Soil Extract Arginine (CDSEA) broth containing (gm/L), Sodium nitrate- 2.0 gm, Di potassium hydrogen phosphate- 1.0 gm, Magnesium sulphate- 0.5 gm, Potassium chloride- 0.5 gm, Ferrous sulphate- 0.01 gm, Soluble starch- 30.0 gm, L-arginine- 0.15 gm, Soil extract- 50.0 ml for detection of extracellular production of arginase. After inoculation the flask was incubated at 28±2°C for 8 days in BOD incubators. Quantification of extracellular arginase produced by *Streptomyces* sp. was done in cell free culture broth obtained by centrifugation of culture broth at 5000 rpm for 10 minutes at 4°C followed by filtration of

supernatant through Millipore syringe filters (0.22µm).

L-arginase activity: An aliquot of 0.8 ml of buffered arginine was mixed with 1.0 ml of enzyme and incubated at 37 °C for 30 minute in water bath. On completion of incubation period, 0.2ml of TCA (10% w/v) solution was added to stop the reaction and kept for 10 minutes followed by centrifugation at 10,000 rpm for 10 minutes at 4°C. To 1 ml of supernatant 3ml of chromogenic solution was added and boiled for 15 minutes at 100°C. The absorbance was read at 525 nm using Picodrop spectrophotometer. Reaction blank was processed as above, with addition of TCA before incubation. One Unit (U) of L Arginase activity is considered here as 1µmole of urea produced per minute at 37°C.

Purification of L-arginase: Purification of L-arginase was done using ammonium sulphate salting out method, complete precipitation of protein was achieved at 75 % saturation. Followed by dialysis of precipitated crude enzyme was done using 10 KD a cut-off dialysis membrane in 0.001 M PBS, overnight. Separation and purification of L-arginase was done using Sephadex G-100 column and eluted using Tris-HCL buffer, pH 8.0. The steps of purification were performed in sequential manner described above.

Anti-microbial assay of L-arginase using agar well assay: Antimicrobial activity of L-arginase against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus mutans* was studied using agar well diffusion technique. Agar well was made on Blood Agar and Brain Heart Infusion Agar media plates using sterilized cork borer and 50 µL of L-arginase (20U) was dispensed in each well. Thereafter, the spore suspension of bacteria prepared in Tween 20 - water blanks (100:1v/v) of density equivalent to 0.5 OD at 700nm was spread uniformly on the surface of media plates. The inoculated plated were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. Subsequently, plates were observed for formation of zone of inhibition in growth of micro-organisms.

Biofilm inhibition assay: Quantitative estimation of anti-biofilm potential of L-arginase was studied 96 well, flat bottom micro-titre plates. 100 µL of Brain heart infusion broth containing 2% (w/v) was dispensed in each well and was subsequently inoculated with 50 µL of bacterial spore suspension. 32 well were kept as control to which L-arginase was not added and the volume was made up using PBS (pH 7.2), 50µL of L-arginase was added in each well in increasing concentration (1U, 5U, 10 U, 15 U, 20 U, 25 U). Incubation was done at 37°C for 24 hour, thereby

the supernatant was removed from each well and washed thrice with sterilized PBS. The biofilms were stained with 150µl of Gram's Crystal Violet for 1-2 minutes. The excess stain was removed by washing. The biofilm formed was estimated by dissolving it using 30% (v/v) glacial acetic acid. The elute from each well was centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 10 min to remove debris. The absorbance of dissolved Gram's Crystal Violet dye was read at 630 nm. The percentage of biofilm formed was calculated using equation^[8] Biofilm formation (%)= (Optical density in presence of L-arginase/ Optical density of blank)x 100

RESULTS:

Extracellular production of L arginase by *Streptomyces* sp. HAB 228 on CDSEA broth had yield of 0.28 ± 0.007 gm growth (dry weight). The cell free culture broth displayed 137.8 ± 2.8 U/ml of L-arginase activity. On purification of enzyme the purity reached 82.3 % with recovery of 57% enzyme.

L-arginase produced by *Streptomyces* sp. HAB 228 was found to inhibit the growth of all herein tested pathogenic bacteria, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus mutans*, under *in vitro* conditions (Graph 1). The extent of inhibition noticed on different growth media differed as the zone of inhibition of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* in Brain Heart Infusion Agar was 25 ± 3 mm (Figure 1), while it was 9 ± 2 mm on Blood agar. Similarly the zone of inhibition with *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus mutans* was found more on BHI media as compared to blood agar.

Pseudomonas aeruginosa, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus mutans* were found to form biofilms on microtitre plates when studied under Stereo-microscope (Figure 2). The inhibition in formation of biofilm was noticed on addition of L-arginase along with bacterial culture *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus mutans*. The biofilm formation was measurably reduced in case of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* followed by *Streptococcus mutans* (Table 1).

DISCUSSION:

Biofilm contains gradation of nutrients and oxygen on moving from exterior to interior. Hence, bacteria located in nutrient deprived area have reduced metabolic activity as well as slow growth rate.^[9] These bacteria can thus be considered as dormant and hence may render resistance and tolerance to antibiotics.

Bacteria in different layers of biofilm communicate with each other through various

Graph1: Inhibition in growth of pathogenic bacteria by L- arginase produced by *Streptomyces* sp. HAB 228 using Agar well diffusion technique on solid media under *in vitro* conditions

Table 1: Effect of purified L- arginase on biofilm produced by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Streptococcus mutans* and *Staphylococcus aureus*.

L- arginase (U*)	Inhibition in Biofilm Formation (%)		
	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	<i>Streptococcus mutans</i>	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
1	-	2±1	-
5	16±4	6±2	-
10	23±9	11±5	2±0
15	34±7	19±4	7±0
20	53±5	48±7	18±3
25	57±4	54±6	29±4

* One Unit (U) of L-arginase activity is considered here as 1 μmole of urea produced per minute at 37°C.

Figure 1: Zone of inhibition of growth *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* in Brain Heart Infusion Agar, incubated for 24 hours at 37°C well diameter 8 mm.

biomolecules. Removal of such molecules from the vicinity of bacteria may be promising for controlling biofilm formation. Other approaches may comprise using enzymes able to degrade biofilm matrix chiefly composed of extracellular DNA, protein, exopolysaccharides and dead cells.^[10]L-arginase was analysed for its inhibitory effect on both planktonic cells and biofilm.

Herein tested bacteria *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus mutans* are amongst commonest pathogens related to nosocomial infections.^[11] Treatment of staphylococcal infections poses challenges due to its resistance to antibiotics, multiplicity of virulence factors and its ability to form a biofilm.^[12,13]The growth of microorganisms may be accentuated by Blood agar, the medium enriched with high protein and essential growth factors.^[14] Although it is evidenced herein in

Figure 2: Biofilm formed by *Streptococcus mutans* on micro titre plate grown in BHI medium (a) Control: Not treated with L-arginase; (b) Treated with 25 U of L-arginase.

this research that L-arginase has proven role in minimizing the arginine availability but it may be compromised due to additional sources of its availability and hence there is noted lesser inhibition in blood agar as compared to BHI media.

Microbial biofilms have multidimensional structures covered with viscous polymeric milieu with different phenotype, genetic composition and functional expression as protein synthesis in comparison to its planktonic form.^[15,16]

Bacterial proteins such as fibronectin-binding protein A (FnBPA) help bacteria to resist mechanical disruption further blocking diffusion of natural and artificial antimicrobial agents.^[17,18] Our study reported activity of L-arginase against planktonic stage along with inhibition of biofilms produced by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus mutans* at different concentration although extent of inhibition increased with enzyme units initially which got stabilized at higher concentration.

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that the novel strategies for treatment, as have been adopted and are usually naturally preferable, should be using enzymes in infective cases as these may be better tolerated, acceptable and user friendly than the existing antibiotics due to their inherent known limitations. However, while underlining the need for further necessary studies, it is also inferred that the pharmacologically suited, disease specific and system

efficient strategies for synergistically active combined treatments i.e. using enzymes along with the existing norms may also be considered especially for those ailments associated with blood abnormalities. These recommendations need support of further studies prior to field level testing.

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